

Common Acceptable Cuisine in Multicultural Countries: Towards Building the National Food Identity

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Abstract : Common acceptable cuisine usually discussed in the multicultural/ethnic nation as it represents the process of sharing acceptable cuisine among the ethnic groups. The common acceptable cuisine also consider as a precursor that takes place in the process of constructing the national food identity within ethnic groups in the multicultural countries which denotes to social integration, reputable and nation building. More precisely, the adaptation of certain ethnic cuisine through types of food, methods of cooking, ingredients and eating decorum by ethnic groups is believed creating or enhancing the process of formation on common acceptable cuisines in a multicultural country. In line with this, Malaysia as the multicultural country without doubt is continuing to experience a cross-culturing processes among the ethnic groups in term of culture, including cuisine therefore the concept that have been highlighted can suitably be investigated. Owing to that, this study empirically investigate the adaptation level of Malay, Chinese and Indian chefs on each other ethnic cuisine attributes toward the beliefs of formation on common acceptable cuisine in Malaysia.

Keywords : Common acceptable cuisine, adaptation, ethnic, food, identity

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